

THE IMPORTANCE OF SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE APPROACHES IN CC(U)S PROJECTS, EXAMPLES FROM THREE HORIZON EUROPE PROJECTS: HERCCULES, ENCASE and CaLby2030

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents an overview of the results of research activities on public perceptions and citizens engagements in three research and innovation industrial projects related to CCUS technologies granted under the Horizon Europe (HE) programme: HERCCULES, ENCASE and CaLby2030. In particular, methodologies, approaches and first results from the current activities on society's and relevant stakeholders' perceptions of CCUS technologies, and examples of involvement of the society are described. While HERCCULES project includes social acceptance and community engagement and it reveals both opportunities and challenges for CCUS acceptance, ENCASE empathised the importance of co-creation process. In CaLby2030 the approach provides insight for considering local industrial dynamic and public perceptions, which can serve as a potential adaptation to the Emilia-Romagna context. Across all these three projects, it emerges that effective CCUS deployment requires not only technological innovation, but it demands a deep understanding of social perceptions, trust-building, and inclusive engagement strategies. These projects collectively show that a one-size-fits-all approach to social engagement is insufficient and engagement strategies must be tailored to the specific social, cultural, economic and political contexts of each region, and stakeholders priorities. The social activities in these projects aim to provide empirically-based recommendations for the design of strategies for involving local communities and relevant local and regional stakeholders from the beginning of the process applicable also in the Emilia-Romagna region.

INTRODUCTION

Negative societal perceptions and lack of societal involvement by affected stakeholders and communities can be a significant barrier to the development and deployment of CCUS technologies. While the techno-economic case for CCUS is fairly clear as it is aligned with climate goals and is currently high on the political agenda with ambitious targets set by national governments and the EU [1], the nascent policy framework is still evolving [2] and issues of public support and societal legitimacy remain largely unresolved. In the worst case, a lack of community and relevant

stakeholder acceptance can contribute to the stallment or even cancellation of a CCUS project [3, 4]. Hence, understanding the factors influencing community and stakeholder acceptance of CCUS industrial projects is key for projects' planning, development and implementation. This includes understanding society's as well as relevant stakeholders' perceptions of CCUS technologies as well as clear and transparent communication and strategies to engage with local communities, policy, and societal stakeholders at a very early stage in order to align the trajectories of technological innovation with the values and needs of policy, affected industries, and civil society. Promoting the inclusion of a multiplicity of actors, with different interests and priorities, facilitates the acceptance and legitimacy of the technologies at stake [e.g. 5, 6, 7, 8]. Aligning the trajectories of innovation as closely as possible with the values and needs of all stakeholders is necessary to facilitate the acceptability and legitimacy of the technologies involved.

To address this need, applied research projects addressing CC(U)S topics and supported by the European Commission in the Horizon Europe (HE) framework are an important platform.

HERCCULES

HERCCULES project approaches the question of feasibility and implementation of CCUS technology along the full CCUS value-chain including capture, use, transport and storage. It aims to establish a new, integrated and replicable approach for the implementation of the full CCUS chain in two strategic economy sectors - cement and energy from waste (EfW) - in Italy and Greece (Fig. 1), where the industrial potential of CCUS remains largely unexplored.

In Italy, the project focuses its research and implementation activities with three main demonstration sites: (1) Vernasca cement plant, (where a pilot CO₂ capture plant will be tested), (2) the "Silla 2" waste-to-energy plant located in the north-west of Milan and (3) the off-shore storage site of Ravenna (already in use since August 2024 by the ENI-SNAM pilot project). In Greece, the project activities are focused on the TITAN Thessaloniki cement plant and the offshore storage site of Prinus in the region of Kavala/Thasos. The aim is to promote and accelerate a first-of-a-kind industrial-scale CCUS project to decarbonize hard-to-abate industry, in particular cement production and energy-from-waste (EfW).

The HERCCULES project includes a "Social acceptance and community engagement" component (i.e. work package WP8) that aims to assess societal readiness of CCUS technologies in order to create awareness and to gain feedback on the societal impact for the proposed technical solutions. While HERCCULES's activities encompass the full CCUS value-chain, WP8 focuses on public attitudes, community, and stakeholder concerns and needs mainly regarding the offshore storage of carbon capture due to the fact that this is where possible negative perceptions are often most pronounced and visible [9, 10]. The goal is to derive empirically-driven strategies to enhance the participation of the local communities and stakeholders in the regions under study. In 2024, the HERCCULES WP8 project team published two reports analyzing citizens' and stakeholders' perceptions of CCUS. One report, focusing on detailed regional profiles of the HERCCULES storage sites, highlights the growing interest in CCUS among stakeholders in the Emilia-Romagna region. Data collected through stakeholder interviews and analysis of documents, policies, and media show that political and industrial stakeholders recognise the potential of CCUS to reduce CO₂ emissions in hard-to-abate industries. However, there is some contention between proponents of CCUS - mainly political and industrial actors - and environmental activists who are concerned that prioritizing CCUS could hinder broader decarbonization efforts [11]. The report also highlights the importance of considering socio-political and socio-economic contexts when assessing stakeholders' and citizens' perceptions of CCUS technologies.

Fig 1: Location of HERCCULES CO₂ storage sites. Source: Kantel et al. 2024, p. 10.

A second report from the HERCCULES project [12] presents the results of four public opinion surveys conducted to assess public acceptance of CCUS in Greece and Italy (Fig. 2). The study combines data from a representative national survey (about 1,000 respondents per country) and a regional survey (about 500 respondents per region). The regions surveyed - Eastern Macedonia and Thrace (Greece) and Emilia-Romagna (Italy) - are key locations for the planned CO₂ storage under HERCCULES. Consistent with other recent studies, the results show a low level of public awareness of CCUS, with 41-56% of respondents stating that they had never heard of it. Italians generally perceive themselves as slightly more familiar with CCUS than Greek respondents.

Fig 2: Familiarity with CCUS, source: Düttschke et al. 2024, p. 15

The results indicate mixed socio-political acceptance of CCUS as a technology to reduce CO₂ emissions (ibid.). Italian respondents showed a more positive attitude towards CCUS, with over 70% of valid responses in both regional and national samples rating it as a "good" or "very good" option for mitigating climate change. In Greece, the national sample was also somewhat positive, with 48% of respondents viewing CCUS as a good or very good option. However, in Eastern Macedonia and Thrace, positive ratings dropped to 40%, making them the most skeptical group, with 28% expressing doubts. In all samples, a significant proportion of respondents remained undecided (>32%), probably reflecting the low level of familiarity with the CCUS. In particular, the larger geographical area of Emilia-Romagna compared to Eastern Macedonia and Thrace may have

influenced responses, as participants from the Greek region live closer to the proposed storage site, potentially increasing their concerns.

In terms of local implementation, community acceptance of CCUS was generally high in all surveys (Fig. 3). In Emilia-Romagna, 67% of respondents found local implementation "rather acceptable" or "acceptable," which was close to the 71% in the national samples. However, acceptance was lower in Eastern Macedonia and Thrace, where only 51% expressed support. Despite these regional differences, the overall results suggest a promising level of local acceptance for CCUS projects (ibid.).

Fig 3: Acceptance of potential implementation of CCUS in the respective study areas. Source: Dütschke et al. 2024, p. 19.

In Italy, particularly in Emilia-Romagna, the survey results indicate a favorable environment for engagement and participation in CCUS technologies. In contrast, opinions in Greece, especially in Eastern Macedonia and Thrace, are somewhat less supportive. However, despite lower familiarity with CCUS, a majority of respondents in the Greek region expressed spontaneous support for local CCUS development. This support should be viewed in the context of low awareness levels, suggesting that measured acceptance is likely based on first impressions rather than informed decisions. As such, these perceptions are expected to evolve dynamically over time, making public and stakeholder engagement strategies relevant.

Part of the project is also the creation of Regional Stakeholder Committees as a project platform for regular exchange between the project team and the stakeholders in the regions involved. In this committee, the representatives of the quadruple-helix from research, government, industry and associations are involved. They have already met twice and they will meet yearly with the aim of hearing the latest on technological and application developments of the project and discussing social acceptability.

Student engagement in HERCCULES

As part of the HERCCULES project, an educational initiative was carried out in collaboration with the POLIMI School of Design to explore the role of communication and public perception in CCUS technologies. This initiative aimed to engage students in the process of disseminating CCUS knowledge and investigating how the general public perceives this emerging technology. The training and workshop program, held from June 3rd to 7th, 2024, was designed to provide third-year undergraduate students with the tools to understand and communicate CCUS technologies effectively. It included expert lectures from energy and environmental specialists, interactive discussions, and a hands-on project development phase. The initiative began and ended with a

Mentimeter session designed to evaluate how students' perceptions of CCUS evolved throughout the workshop. Nine student groups, consisting of 44 participants, were assigned the task of developing multimedia content aimed at explaining CCUS to the general public. The content included infographics, PowerPoint presentations, videos, and a game, all created under the supervision of academic staff and industry experts. The workshop concluded with the selection and awarding of the three most outstanding projects, recognizing creativity, clarity, and effectiveness in communication.

The workshop revealed several critical insights regarding the communication of CCUS. In particular:

- **Clarity and accessibility:** students identified that simplifying technical language and using visual storytelling were key to making CCUS concepts more understandable to the public.
- **Trust and credibility:** the importance of the credibility of the communicators was a recurring theme. Students concluded that public engagement efforts should emphasise transparency and authoritative sources.
- **Concerns and barriers:** initial student perceptions mirrored broader public concerns about CCUS, including potential environmental risks and economic feasibility. After engaging with the material, many students shifted toward a more positive outlook on the technology.

This model has been already replicated in other educational settings (see ENCASE project) to foster broader awareness of CCUS technologies. A selection of the multimedia materials created during the workshop is available on Zenodo. Figure 4 represents an example of the student-created content that highlights the main aspects of CCUS communication.

Fig 4: Example of the student-created content

Also, a regional citizen engagement strategy has been developed to guide subsequent citizen engagement activities within the HERCCULES project throughout the upcoming two years, including focus groups and public events.

ENCASE

The ENCASE project aims to advance CCS research and technology in Europe. It brings together various stakeholders, including research institutions, operators, manufacturers, academia, and SMEs, to enhance competitiveness in the CCS industry. One of the ENCASE work packages requires five European research infrastructures RIs (IFE in Norway, TNO in the Netherlands, NEL TUV in the UK, INERIS in France and POLIMI-LEAP-GREENTECH in Italy) to conduct co-creation activities with the local stakeholders.

While government regulation and market dynamics play a vital role in driving green transitions, research increasingly highlights the potential of collaborative governance. This approach unites public and private stakeholders to identify challenges and develop and implement shared solutions collaboratively [13, 14, 15]. Among collaborative governance approaches, co-creation involves scientists, private stakeholders and lay actors (e.g., citizens, neighbourhoods, community organisations) in collective efforts that involve sharing experiences, ideas, and resources. This process can stimulate mutual learning and bottom-up innovation [16]. In co-creation, participating actors engage in creative problem-solving that mobilises actor-specific assets (e.g., knowledge, expertise, authority, creativity, and finance) to develop needs-based solutions. In ENCASE, we aim to explore whether, how and under what circumstances co-creation might work to favour green transition, alongside favouring the integration of research infrastructure in their local communities and increasing awareness of CCUS. What is present here is still preliminary and we are still in the phase of conducting the co-creation process.

Background Information

The task shared with the ENCASE partners was structured in the following way: each RI, after two pieces of training on how to develop co-creation processes, chose a social problem they would like to address and the stakeholders involved to address it. In the project funding, each organisation had a set amount of resources (financial and work hours) to work on the selected problem and develop co-creation solutions. Social science researchers from the Open University (project partner) are supporting the RI in planning, developing and implementing activities alongside exploring whether, how and under what circumstances. Below, we present the current updates of the five research organisations and their co-creation projects.

INERIS (France): facilitating national-level CCS discussion

INERIS (Institut National De L'environnement Industriel Et Des Risques – The French National Institute for Industrial Environment and Risks headquartered in Verneuil-en-Halatte, 70 km north of Paris) decided to focus on the lack of public debate on CCS in France. They plan to start the national-level debate on CCS by engaging the advisory board and INERIS connections to explore and develop a policy brief and policy actions.

NEL TUV (UK): raising awareness of CCUS through art

NEL TUV (The National Engineering Laboratory TÜV SÜD, suburbs of Glasgow) identified a lack of awareness of CCUS in the local community. To tackle this problem NEL TUV introduced the idea of linking engineering and art by co-creating a book for primary school children. The development of this book will involve artists, teachers, primary school children, and higher education institutions from Scotland and England. NEL TUV is planning to collect artwork for this book through interactive events organised for primary school children at the Glasgow Science Festival in June 2025 and an art competition for students enrolled in Scottish universities.

TNO (Netherlands): increasing trust in CCUS

TNO (Netherlands Organisation for Applied Scientific Research, in Rijswijk) has identified scepticism and lack of trust towards CCUS as the problem they want to address. They suggested co-creating a permanent interactive exhibition at the Energy Cave, a sustainability-themed interactive exhibition space managed by a local non-profit organisation located on the ground floor of the TNO office, to increase public trust in CCUS. TNO has conducted preliminary discussions with the local population to explore their understanding of CCUS and will use the results of those discussions to inform the exhibition.

POLIMI-LEAP-Clust-ER Greentech (Italy): Energy Transition Stories

POLIMI-LEAP-Greentech (three organisations – a branch of The Polytechnic University of Milan, a research centre conducting green energy research Laboratorio Energia Ambiente Piacenza, and an association of members working on energy and sustainable development, all located in Emilia-Romagna region) identified a lack of knowledge of CCUS and sustainability issues among young

adults as the issue to address. In cooperation with the local council, they have organised a competition among secondary school students in the city of Piacenza “Stories of energy transition”: the challenge of sustainability. Students will create an artwork (video or image) related to sustainable energy transitions. Winners will be selected by open voting and by a committee. Currently, three classes (around 55 students) from the local high schools (scientific lyceums) are involved. So far, POLIMI-LEAP-Greentech has developed a website advertising the competition (Fig. 4 <https://contest.tecnopolo.piacenza.it/>), an introductory co-creation workshop for the students (Fig.5) to explain the process and the rules and a workshop in February 2025 on Sustainability transitions. More activities are planned with the students, and a final event in May 2025. Photos and videos of the winning teams will be showcased at the final ENCASE meeting in Brussels in 2026.

Fig 4: Schematic map of the POLIMI-LEAP-GREENTECH co-creation process as displayed on the website.

Fig 5: The first co-creation workshop with the students on 14 November 2025 in Piacenza.

IFE (Norway): Project Stardust

IFE (Institute for Energy Technology located in Kjeller, 20 km north-east of Oslo) identified as a problem the lack of young adults pursuing STEM (science, technology, engineering, mathematics) disciplines and STEM-related professions after school. In collaboration with an external expert experienced in engaging students, one schoolteacher, and several staff members, IFE has developed an activity for raising the interest of young adults in science. The activity involved students collecting dust particles on the school roof and examining them for traces of micrometeorites (Fig. 6) using microscopes. IFE ran 4 sessions with the students between September and October 2024:

one information session where the activity was explained, one session dedicated to collecting the dust particles on the school roof, one session studying the collected samples, and one final session where students reflected on the topics of science and sustainability. As a result, students identified 42 samples of micrometeorites and received posters with high-resolution photos. 30 secondary school students have participated in the activity. IFE plans to undertake the activity in the other two local schools during Spring 2025.

Fig 6: Image left: Students are collecting particles from the school roof to be examined under the microscope. Image right: Students are studying images of the particles to identify micrometeorites.

CaLby2030

The project CaLby2030 focuses on the decarbonisation of high-emission sectors using Circulating Fluidised Bed (CFB) – Calcium Looping (CaL) technologies to be demonstrated at TRL 6 in cement (Germany), steel (Sweden) and power (Spain) plants. In addition to analysing technical aspects for the future commercialisation of this technology, the project also proposes a survey of social acceptance and preferences for the potential implementation of CCUS in the case of the power plant of La Pereda, Asturias (Spain), which is being reconverted from coal to a biomass-fired power plant and is expected to be functioning as such in 2030. The proposed study focuses on the acceptance of this technology for a specific case study and on the potential trade-off between “zero” emissions for alternatives of utilisation of CO₂ for synthetic fuels and “negative” emissions for alternatives of storage of CO₂ in three different regions in Europe (Spain, the coast of France and the North Sea in Norway). The social acceptability study in CaLby2030 proposes the use of stated preferences methods [17], specifically a choice experiment, to examine these trade-offs between alternative storage and utilisation scenarios accompanying the development of the CaL-based CO₂ capture technology developed in La Pereda. The experiment is being designed and implemented in a survey of the populations of adults (>18 years) of Spain. It will focus on different levels of acceptability and preferences associated with respondents’ distance to the power plant, respondents’ distance to the storage sites and respondents’ perception of the technology in general. The study also includes several questions that identify respondents’ attitudes and perception of the problem of climate change in general with the goal of testing whether this has an impact on the social acceptability of the hypothetical CCUS programs in La Pereda. Choice experiments are a survey-based technique in which a series of alternatives characterised by multiple attributes are presented to a sample of individuals from a target population [18]. Groups of alternatives in hypothetical scenarios constructed according to an experimental design are presented to respondents who are asked to choose the

most preferred alternative, to rank them or to rate them according to a prespecified scale. The choice (most preferred alternative) is the most usual format if the scenario implies the “hypothetical” purchase of the alternatives. The social acceptability choice experiment in CaLby2030 is being currently developed and has been preceded by a systematic literature review that has identified barriers and drivers of CCUS [19]. Based on this literature review and on consultation with experts and focus groups, the choice experiment of the CaLby2030 survey includes four attributes to describe the alternatives of the hypothetical implementation of the CaL-based CO₂ capture technology in La Pereda: (i) the amount of CO₂ captured (99%, 95%, 90% or 85% of CO₂ emissions per year); (ii) the destination of the CO₂ captured (use for the manufacturing of synthetic fuels, storage in the province of Burgos (Spain), storage in the coast of France and storage in the Norwegian North Sea); (iii) employment created in the plant (40, 60, 80 or 100 permanent employees); and (iv) an one-time increase in the income tax to fund the program (€50, €100, €200, €400). The experimental design combines these attributes and their possible values in choice situations involving two alternatives plus the status quo alternative, for which no CCUS program is implemented in La Pereda. A total of 16 choice situations have been generated and they have been blocked in four questionnaire types, containing each four choice situations. Thus, each survey respondent faces four choice situations in which one alternative has to be chosen out of the three presented. The experimental design guarantees that all attribute levels are presented throughout the 16 alternatives in an efficient and balanced way. Figure 7 shows an example of a preliminary design of a choice situation of two alternatives (A and B) plus the status quo (alternative C) from the CaLby2030 survey. The other 15 choice situations include different attribute levels and combinations of attribute levels according to the experimental design.

Characteristics	Alternative A	Alternative B	Alternative C
Captured CO ₂	 95%	0%	
Destination of captured CO ₂	 Underground storage in the North Sea	No change	
Employment generated (permanent annual jobs)	 100	No change	
Increase in income tax, only in 2025	 400 euros	No change	
Which alternative would you choose?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Fig 7: choice scenario preliminary design for the CaLby2030 survey

Although still ongoing, the study of social acceptability of La Pereda represents an opportunity to obtain a direct assessment of how the general population perceives the potential implementation of CCUS in a real case of CaL-based technology development. We expect to provide relevant information to policy-makers on the key aspects of the technology which would attain a higher social support for its future commercialisation. This case study also contributes to the practitioners’ toolkit by testing the choice experiment methodology as a versatile technique that potentially provides information about the trade-offs that lay people may have about alternatives of “zero” emissions versus alternatives of “negative” emission but with risks associated with storage.

The developed methodology applied in the case of La Pereda in Spain, has been critically reviewed and adapted to the context of Piacenza, Italy. Piacenza, located in the Emilia-Romagna region, hosts a strong industrial reality, rooted in Piacenza's historical role as a "capital of energy" [20], with a well-established mechanical sector which has long defined its economic landscape. In this context, Iren, a key industrial partner of CaLby2030 project, operates a waste-to-energy (WtE) plant that represents an opportunity for the application of the CaLby2030 capture technology in the near future, enhancing its role in the decarbonization efforts of the region.

Point of attention to transfer the analysis to Emilia-Romagna case study

Piacenza is a medium town of approximately 103,000 residents (2024), and has a mix of industrial and agricultural activities, contributing to its CO₂ emissions profile. According to regional environmental reports [21], Piacenza's industrial sector accounted for approximately 32% of total CO₂ emissions in the province. Iren's WtE plant in Piacenza plays a crucial role in waste management by converting non-recyclable waste into energy. However, the plant is also a source of CO₂ emissions, and the introduction of CaL technology could significantly enhance its environmental performance. Given the increasing public concerns on environmental sustainability, the success of such a technology deployment depends not only on technical feasibility but also on social acceptance among local stakeholders. Understanding public attitudes toward carbon capture technologies is crucial for their successful implementation, as perceived environmental risks and economic benefits strongly influence acceptance levels. Following the methodological approach used in La Pereda, the potential implementation of CaL technology in Emilia-Romagna with Iren as first potential case study was initiated due to the need for a structured approach to understand public attitudes and local perceptions and preferences regarding the potential implementation of CaL technology at Iren's plant. With the aim of exploring how different factors influence the local communities in the acceptance of CO₂ capture technology integration in Emilia-Romagna, the following key attributes have been included in the study:

- CO₂ capture efficiency: the percentage of CO₂ captured (ranging from 85% to 99%), similar to La Pereda case, ensures comparability.
- Destination of captured CO₂: options include (i) utilisation for synthetic fuel production, (ii) storage in geological formations within the Po Valley (if feasible), and (iii) transport for offshore storage in the Adriatic Sea.
- Local economic impact: number of new permanent jobs created at the Iren plant as a result of the implementation of CaL technology (2-10 employees).
- Financial mechanisms to cover the extra costs: either a one-time increase in municipal taxes or waste fees to finance the project (e.g., €20, €50, €100, €200) or an instalment plan.

As a first testing ground, the study will target a representative sample of Piacenza residents (>18 years), with specific attention to stakeholders living in proximity to Iren's plant and those with professional links to the waste management and energy sectors. The survey will also collect data on respondents' environmental attitudes, knowledge of CCUS technologies, and trust in local institutions to manage climate initiatives effectively. The adaptation of CaLby2030's methodology to Emilia-Romagna also considered the historical and institutional context of Iren's operations in the region. Iren has been actively engaged in circular economy projects and renewable energy investments, positioning itself as a progressive actor in the transition towards sustainable waste management. However, past experiences in Italy indicate that public opposition to waste-to-energy projects often stems from concerns about air pollution, waste transport, and potential health risks. To address these concerns, the approach of the study was to also integrate insights from the HERCCULES project, which highlighted key lessons from student engagement. These findings emphasised that the credibility and trustworthiness of those conducting the activities and the

transparency in communicating them are crucial aspects of public engagement. Building on these principles, the approach of the study is to integrate: a) Stakeholder dialogues: engaging local policymakers, environmental organizations, and citizen groups in workshops to discuss CCUS applications at Iren's plant; b) Transparent communication: providing clear information on the expected environmental benefits of CaL technology, particularly its potential to reduce CO₂ emissions and enhance the sustainability of the WtE process; c) Comparative risk perception analysis: evaluating public perceptions of CO₂ utilisation versus long-term storage, particularly in relation to the feasibility and safety of underground CO₂ storage sites in the Emilia-Romagna.

By applying the CaLby2030 methodology to investigate social acceptability in Emilia-Romagna, expectations in terms of outcomes and policy implications for integrating CCUS in waste-to-energy operations will help in: a) Identifying which CCUS pathways (utilization or storage) are more socially acceptable in the region; b) Informing local and regional policy frameworks for low-carbon waste management strategies; c) Strengthening engagement with the community by addressing concerns and highlighting the benefits of the proposed technology. The adaptation of the methodology from La Pereda to Emilia-Romagna (Piacenza) highlighted key considerations: while some factors, such as general awareness of climate change and the importance of emissions reduction, were consistent across both cases, other aspects required a more tailored approach. The different industrial contexts, public attitudes toward waste-to-energy versus biomass energy, and regional policy frameworks necessitated a deeper investigation into local socio-political dynamics and economic priorities. Furthermore, lessons learned from this adaptation will inform future methodological refinements, enabling the approach to be customized for diverse European contexts where industry, public engagement traditions, and regulatory landscapes vary significantly, ensuring the scalability and effectiveness of CCUS deployment strategies.

CONCLUSIONS

This study highlights the critical role of social engagement in the successful deployment of CCUS technologies across Europe, with a focus on Southern Europe, drawing from insights gained through the HERCCULES, ENCASE, and CaLby2030 projects. Each project provides a unique perspective on the societal dimensions of CCUS, contributing to a broader understanding of how public perceptions, stakeholder engagement, and local socio-economic contexts can influence the adoption of these technologies.

Across all these three projects, a clear pattern emerges: effective CCUS deployment requires more than technological innovation, it demands a deep understanding of social perceptions, trust-building, and inclusive engagement strategies. The research underscores that public acceptance cannot be assumed, especially in regions where awareness of CCUS remains low or where historical concerns about industrial activities persist. Engagement strategies must be tailored to the specific social, economic, and political contexts of each region.

The case of Emilia-Romagna Region, has emerged as a particularly relevant testing ground for understanding these dynamics. In the HERCCULES project, activities revealed both opportunities and challenges for CCUS acceptance. While there is growing institutional support and recognition of CCUS's potential for industrial decarbonization, environmental concerns among civil society highlight the need for transparent, authoritative, and participatory communication strategies. The involvement of students from the POLIMI School of Design showcased the importance of engaging younger generations through creative educational methods, fostering greater awareness and

understanding of CCUS technologies. This initiative served as the first example of this engagement format, which was later adopted in subsequent projects such as ENCASE, highlighting its effectiveness in enhancing public understanding and participation.

The ENCASE project further emphasised the importance of co-creation processes, where local stakeholders and citizens actively contribute to shaping technological solutions. Co-creation activities might be a successful way of increasing the knowledge and awareness about CCUS when a wide variety of stakeholders are involved as the experiences in Piacenza with the "Stories of Energy Transition" competition involving young generations. They are an important way of involving the communities; especially a mix of bottom-up and top-down approaches in the co-creation process should be favoured to provide the possibility of stakeholders to take decisions and at the same time advance the processes. To be successful adequate long-term funding should be provided and training should be put in place for supporting the development of co-creation skills, and a long-term plan should be established to achieve successful stakeholders' involvement.

In the CaLby2030 project, the methodology developed for La Pereda (Spain) served as a foundational point of reference for reflections on its potential adaptation to the Emilia-Romagna context. This approach provided initial insights for considering local industrial dynamics and public perceptions, particularly in light of IREN's presence in the Piacenza area and its relevance within the regional energy landscape. While some concerns were consistent across both regions (such as the need for transparency and trust) others required a more nuanced approach. Differences in industrial backgrounds, local attitudes toward waste-to-energy plants, and regional policy frameworks necessitated a tailored strategy to engage stakeholders effectively.

Collectively, these projects reveal that a one-size-fits-all approach to social engagement in CCUS is not viable. Instead, successful CCUS deployment depends on adaptive methodologies that account for local specificities, cultural contexts, and stakeholder priorities. The lessons learned from the Emilia-Romagna experience can serve as a model for broader applications across Europe, offering key lessons that could be expanded across Europe. These findings emphasize several critical considerations: outreach strategies need to be tailored to reflect regional socio-economic and cultural realities, trust and transparency must be prioritized to foster public acceptance, and co-creation processes involving industry, government, academia, and civil society are essential for mutual learning and collaboration. Additionally, recognizing socio-political and economic factors (such as regional industrial histories and economic structures) helps to address specific concerns and opportunities for CCUS deployment.

In conclusion, embedding social engagement into CCUS strategies strengthens public trust, enhances societal readiness, and ensures that technological innovations are aligned with regional values and needs. The insights gained from Emilia-Romagna, combined with broader lessons from HERCCULES, ENCASE, and CaLby2030, underscore the necessity of integrating community participation into Europe's path toward industrial decarbonization.

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HERCCULES

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